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Assessment of Information and Communication Technology Tools on Chemistry Teaching and Learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This study examined Information and Communication Technology tools on Chemistry teaching and learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State. Four research questions and hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population of the study comprises of all Chemistry teachers during the 2022/2023 academic session in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. A sample size of 256 (Male 140 and Female 116) Chemistry teachers was obtained using Taro Yamene formula. A 4-point rating scale questionnaire was used. The instrument was validated by two experts. The split-half technique was used to test the reliability and a reliability coefficient of 0.89 for teachers, showed that the instruments are reliable. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions. Hypotheses were tested using z- test at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that ICT facilities such as computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point etc. were available for Chemistry teaching and learning, while projectors, multimedia devices were not available for Chemistry teaching and learning in senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. It was concluded that thought, the use of ICT tools in the study area is low, it has positive and significant impact in students' performance. It was recommended amongst others that; ICT in Education should be a core course for teachers' training programme to adequately prepare teachers on how they can effectively domesticate ICT in their respective discipline while in the classroom.

Keyword: ICT Tools, Teaching, Learning, Chemistry and Teacher

Introduction

One of the notable changes that are peculiar in this 21st century also known as the information age is the dynamic and rapid growth of information Communication Technologies. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has turned the world into a global village and as the days goes by, it gained more ground (Nnaekwe & Ugwu, 2019). Before now, eventually everything was done manually but the advent of ICT has changed the perception and also increases the work speed of so many things in our society today. The growth of every society is ascertained to a degree of communication between the human standards and technical advancement. There is hardly a thing one we do in this new age without using ICT, this is a well-known fact as all human activities is speedily changing into electronic patterns of which education is not left out (Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo, 2021). ICT can be defined as an electronic, and communication devices connected with the social and material life of human which allows individuals to use a wide range of instructional process. ICT tools comprises of all the available equipment used for identification, generation, preservation, conservation, production, storage, packaging, processing, retrieval and dissemination of information that is not limited by time and distance (ThankGod & Innocent, 2021). Ejinwa, (2018) posit that advancement, globalization and new opportunities in education is a result of the blending and frequent use of ICT. For an improvement in works of teachers and students in this information era there is need for the implementation and integration of ICT into the teaching and learning environment as it presents more opportunities (Lawrence & Tar, 2018). The advancement of this era of information interaction and it meeting with telecommunication with the aid of computers has increases the possibility to use different technological tool in teaching and learning situation. The utilization of ICT facilities in the education system shift education from teacher-centered education to learner-centered education. Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo (2021).

Community and individuals are affected in various ways by ICT facilities which surrounds different area like politics, technology, economics, society for transformation globally (ThankGod & Innocent, 2021). The incorporation of information and communication technologies into our education system has bring about exceptional privileges since it has the ability to improve, communicate and bring together people from different locations, both far and near to interact and achieve learning objects in a meaningful way. The use of ICT improves the quality of education, make information accessible and

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

also increase learning opportunities in different subjects. ICT as an innovative method of teaching creates an interactive learning situation facilitate improve thinking ability and make the classroom an environment for educational development. (Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo, 2021). ICT has capability to change the teaching and learning environment from the traditional methods to a new one by teaching, visualizing new learning methods. The use of ICT and other IT communication facilities such as computer, internet, projector in the teaching and learning of Chemistry in secondary schools is more ease and more effective. Therefore, this research work is intended to examine the impact of the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

(Despite the global advancement in technology, the teaching of Chemistry in Nigerian secondary schools particularly in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State has been archaic as they still adopt the old method of teaching of chalkboard and textbooks only (Ejinwa, 2018). They have not yet started using innovative strategies of teaching like use of projects, internet, computers and other ICT facilities (Ejinwa, 2018). A major setback in various classrooms of third world countries and Nigeria in particular is lack of expertise and understanding in applying and incorporating of ICT in teaching pedagogy (Lawrence & Tar, 2018). At present, various challenges such as: lack of ICT facilities, in-service training for teachers and funds from government, made the utilization of ICT in learning still quite low. Furthermore, most students lack the needed tools like android phones, laptops, personal computers (hardware), software and internet access (ThankGod & Innocent, 2021). Students perform poorly in some Chemistry concepts of which the use of the conventional strategy of teaching is lacking but when taught using ICT it has capability in meeting the requirements of new instructional strategies in teaching and learning which will in turn enhance their performance (Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to Assess Information and Communication Technology tools for chemistry teaching and learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. Determine the mean response on level of utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
2. Determine the mean response on level of competence exhibited by teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
3. Identify the challenges in the use of ICT tools in Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean response on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
2. What is the mean response on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
3. What is the mean response on competence of secondary school teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
4. What is the mean response on challenges on the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on competency exhibited in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on the challenges in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

Methodology

This study is descriptive research. The survey designed was used to investigate Assessment of Information and Communication Technology tools for chemistry teaching and learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State. Wali (2019) survey research design is used to ascertain or investigate the current status of a problem by studying a true representative of the population. All Chemistry teachers in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State constitute the population of this study. There are total of 742 Chemistry teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Taro Yamene formula was used to obtain a sample size of 256 Chemistry teachers, out of a population of 742 teachers. Stratified random sampling was used to select the 256 teachers.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean response on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Teachers' Response on Availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Availability of ICT facilities for Chemistry Students	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	
Computer and ICT accessories	3.01	0.83	3.15	0.87	Agree
Projectors and transparencies	2.33	0.68	2.21	0.64	Disagree
Multimedia devices	2.23	0.50	2.00	0.50	Disagree
Internet facilities	2.14	0.52	2.21	0.68	Disagree
Software packages such as Access, Excel, power point etc.	2.91	0.81	2.94	0.90	Agree
Display boards	3.02	0.82	2.70	0.90	Agree
Photocopiers	2.90	0.76	2.96	0.80	Agree
CD and flash drive	2.93	0.84	2.93	0.73	Agree
Total	2.68	0.72	2.64	0.75	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.1 shows that mean values of 3.01, 2.91, 3.02, 2.90 and 2.93 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.33, 2.23 and 2.14 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.83, 0.68, 0.50, 0.52, 0.81, 0.82, 0.76 and 0.84 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. However, mean values of 3.15, 2.94, 2.70, 2.96 and 2.93 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.21, 2.00 and 2.21 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained,

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

that is; 0.83, 0.68, 0.50, 0.52, 0.81, 0.82, 0.76 and 0.84 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Research Question 2

What is the mean response on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Teachers' Response on Utilization of ICT tools for chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Utilization of ICT facilities for Chemistry Students	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	
Computer and ICT accessories	2.95	0.78	2.82	0.88	Agree
Projectors and transparencies	2.32	0.68	2.30	0.58	Disagree
Multimedia devices	2.14	0.63	2.30	0.67	Disagree
Internet facilities	2.38	0.66	2.24	0.72	Disagree
Software packages such as Access, Excel, power point etc.	2.94	0.84	3.10	0.74	Agree
Display boards	3.03	0.86	2.74	0.83	Agree
Photocopiers	2.97	0.85	2.92	0.87	Agree
CD and flash drive	2.81	0.91	2.84	0.70	Agree
Total	2.70	0.78	2.66	0.75	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.2 shows that mean values of 2.95, 2.94, 3.03, 2.97 and 2.81 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.32, 2.14 and 2.38 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.78, 0.68, 0.63, 0.66, 0.84, 0.86, 0.85 and 0.91 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. Mean values of 2.82, 3.10, 2.74, 2.92 and 2.84 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.30, 2.30 and 2.24 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.88, 0.58, 0.67, 0.72, 0.74, 0.83, 0.87 and 0.70 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Research Question 3

What is the mean response on competence of secondary school teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

Table 3: Teachers' Response on the extent to which teachers exhibit competence in the use of ICT tools for chemistry teaching among Secondary School teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Competence in the use of ICT skills in teaching Chemistry	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	
Planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry	2.44	0.71	2.20	0.60	Disagree
Prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry	2.21	0.66	2.25	0.52	Disagree
Using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry	2.37	0.70	2.27	0.65	Disagree
Using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry	2.36	0.61	2.30	0.66	Disagree
Total	2.35	0.67	2.26	0.61	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.3 shows that mean values of 2.44, 2.21, 2.37 and 2.36 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following skills; planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry, prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry, using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry and using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry respectively were lacking for teaching Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.71, 0.66, 0.70 and 0.61 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. The mean values of 2.20, 2.25, 2.27 and 2.30 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following skills; planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry, prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry, using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry and using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry respectively were lacking for teaching Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.60, 0.52, 0.65 and 0.66 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Research Question 4: What is the mean response on challenges on the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

Table 4: Teachers' Response on the Challenges in the use of ICT tools for chemistry teaching in Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Challenges of Using ICT facilities for Chemistry Students	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean	Std. dev.	Mean	Std. dev.	
	\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Lack of trained manpower	2.67	0.84	2.92	0.70	Agree
Lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers	2.66	0.95	3.00	0.75	Agree
Inadequate funding	2.80	0.84	2.97	0.84	Agree
Inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable	3.07	0.91	2.85	0.91	Agree
Lack of regular power supply	2.81	0.92	2.81	0.86	Agree
Inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands-on training	3.17	0.83	2.78	0.80	Agree
Total	2.86	0.66	2.88	0.81	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.4 shows that mean values of 2.67, 2.66, 2.80, 3.07, 2.81 and 3.17 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that the male teachers were of the view that the following; lack of trained manpower, lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of regular power supply and inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands-on training respectively were problems facing Chemistry students and teachers in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.84, 0.95, 0.84, 0.91, 0.92 and 0.83 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. However, the mean values of 2.92, 3.00, 2.97, 2.85, 2.81 and 2.78 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that the female teachers were of the view that the following; lack of trained manpower, lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of regular power supply and inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands-on training respectively were problems facing Chemistry students and teachers in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.70, 0.75, 0.84, 0.91, 0.86 and 0.80 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 5: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the Availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Z-table	Decision
Male teachers	2.68	0.72	140					
Female teachers	2.64	0.75	116	254	0.093	0.43	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.5 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the availability of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (0.43). This shows that male and female

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

teachers agreed that ICT facilities are not adequately available in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 6: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the Utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Ztable	Decision
Male teachers	2.70	0.78	140					
Female teachers	2.66	0.75	116	254	0.097	0.41	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.6 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the utilization of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (0.41). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that ICT facilities are not adequately utilized in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on competency exhibited in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 7: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the level of competence exhibited by teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching in Secondary Schools Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Ztable	Decision
Male teachers	2.35	0.67	140					
Female teachers	2.26	0.61	116	254	0.08	1.13	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.7 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the level of competence exhibited by teachers in the use of ICT facilities in teaching Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (1.13). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that ICT skills are lacking for utilizing ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on the challenges in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 8: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the challenges in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area Bayelsa State.

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Ztable	Decision
Male teachers	2.86	0.66	140					
Female teachers	2.88	0.81	116	254	0.094	0.21	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.8 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the challenges of using ICT facilities in teaching Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa state, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

critical or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (0.21). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that they are confronted by problems using ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in secondary school in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. In research question 1 and hypothesis 1, the study found out that ICT facilities such as; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, while projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Harrison (2002), Ilomaki and Rantanen (2007) who were of the opinion that ICT has the potential of improving student academic performance but its facilities are not adequately and readily available for use in schools. The researchers therefore are of the opinion that ICT is to be used as a method of instruction in the teaching and learning of Chemistry in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

In research question 2 and hypothesis 2, the study found out that ICT facilities such as; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately utilized for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, while projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately utilized for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Again, finding from this study reveal that the extents of the utilization of ICT in the teaching and learning of Chemistry is low, this also agrees with the work of Yusuf, Kajuru and Musa (2013) who reported that only few schools used computer in the teaching and learning of science subjects. The researchers therefore are of the opinion that teachers should employ the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of Chemistry and other science and technology related courses for the benefits of the teaching profession.

In research question 3 and hypothesis 3, the study found out that skills such as; planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry, prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry, using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry and using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry respectively were lacking for teaching Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

In research question 4 and hypothesis 4, the study found out that lack of trained manpower, lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of regular power supply and inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands- on training respectively are the problems facing Chemistry students and teachers in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. This study supports the findings of Unogu (2015), view that teachers should be encouraged to use ICT facilities in teaching some concepts in Chemistry. To achieve this, they should be enlightened on the use of ICT facilities through organized in-service trainings, workshops and seminars.

Conclusion

This study investigated on the impact of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa. From the results and findings of the study it was safe to conclude that though the use of ICT in the study area is low, it has positive and significant impact on the academic performance of students and there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students of the study area. In the circumstance, the researchers are of the opinion that there should be improvement in the use of ICT facilities. Therefore, if schools' instructional materials, workshops and equipment, training and retraining of Chemistry teachers by experts are adequately provided and effectively utilized, it will produce great positive impact on students' achievement and teachers objectives actualized. It will enable better understanding of abstract topics taught by teachers. Teachers however are faced with constraints such as inadequate funding, lack of regular power supply, inadequate workshops and materials, lack of adequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of motivation and incentives among Chemistry teachers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations based on the findings were made:

1. The ability to acquire the ICT devices and appendages rest squarely on what is available to the school management as fund.
2. ICT in Education should be a core course for teachers' training programme to adequately prepare teachers on how they can effectively domesticate ICT in their respective discipline while in the classroom.
3. The Federal Ministry of Works, Housing and Power should work towards stabilizing electricity supply in Nigeria.
4. Government at the federal and state levels should provide computers and other equipment (projector and transparencies) to secondary schools for the integration of ICT into science learning and Government should empower teachers by training them in the use of ICT to teach students.

Assessment of Information and Communication ... (Akomiemie, 2023) DOI:

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References

- Akubuilu, D. U., Nnam, V. I., & Ugo, A. C. (2021). Availability and utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) facilities in teaching of social studies in secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Quest Journals. Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 9(5), 76-83.
- Ejinwa, E. (2018). Evaluation of the use of E- learning as an instructional delivery mode in the National Open University of Nigeria, South-East Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 25(2), 19-23.
- Habiba, H. & Mohammed M. (2021). The Use of ICT in learning English: A Study of students in Moroccan Universities. *SAR Journal*, 4(1), 19-28.
- Harrison, C., Comber, C., Fisher, T., & Haw, K. (2002). Impact: The impact of information and communication technologies on pupil learning and attainment. *Research and Evaluation Journal*, 7(4), 12-19.
- Ilomaki, L., & Rantanen, P. (2007). Intensive use of ICT in school: Developing differences in students' ICT expertise. *Computers & Education*, 48(1), 119–136.
- Ikeobi, I. O. (2010). *Beyond the stereotype: Thoughts and reflections on education*. The CBN Press.
- Joshua, H., Daniel, T., Nnenna, E., & Hua-Jun, F. (2015). Teaching chemistry with computers. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 3(4), 12-18
- Julius, U. U. & Samuel, O. (2018). Teachers' attitude, ICT facilities utilization and teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Advances in Multidisciplinary & Scientific Research Journal*, 4(1), 83-94
- Kamaludeen, S., Sufiyanu, D., Murjanatu, A. & Abubakar, A. A. (2021). Application of ICTs and educational software in teaching physics: Advantages, challenges and proposed solutions. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 8(1), 23-29.
- Lawrence, J.E. & Tar, U.A. (2018). Factors that influence teachers' adoption and integration of ICT in teaching/learning process. *Educational Media International*, 55(4), 1-27.
- Lenka, M. & Lukáš, N. (2021). The current challenges of further education in ICT with the example of the Czech Republic. *Sustainability*, 2(2), 1-13,
- Nnaekwe, U. K. & Ugwu, P. (2019). The concept and application of ICT to teaching/learning process. *International Research Journal of Mathematics, Engineering and IT*, 6(2), 34-39
- Nurul, J. Y. & Ixora, S. M. (2021). Challenges towards the implementation of ICT in chemistry learning: *A J. Phys.* 17(8), 28-32
- Okwuduba, E. N., Offiah F. C. & Madichie C. J. (2018) Effect of computer simulations on secondary school students' academic achievement in chemistry in Anambra State. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 4(4), 284-289,
- Reese, W.J. (2013). In search of American progressives and teachers. *History of education: Journal of History of Education Society*, 42(3), 320-334.
- Thankgod, J. N., & Innocent, O. U. (2021). Availability and utilization of ICT in secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 5(2), 12-21.
- Ugwu, O.I. (2016). Improving instruction in agricultural education in universities through the application of information of ICT and other resources", *Review of Education*, 17(1), 49 – 61.
- Yusuf, I., Kajuru, Y.K. & Musa, M. (2013). The effect of a computer mediated systems teaching approach on mathematics achievement of engineering students in Nigerian polytechnics. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 8(1), 364-370.